

pH biosensor based assay for SLC16A3 using HEK-293 SLC16A3 OE cells

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Assay description

pHluorins are pH-sensitive genetically encoded fluorescent sensors, that allow measurement of intracellular pH in living cells. In particular, pH-Axxam-Sensor (pHAxensor) is a chimera between a pH-insensitive Red fluorescent protein (RFP) and a pHluorin, pH-sensitive Green fluorescent protein (GFP). At acidic pH, pHluorin is quenched, whereas at physiological pH, pHluorin fluorescence increases.

SLC16A3 is a pH-dependent bi-directional lactate transporter. The transport of lactate via SLC16A3 is increased by extracellular acidification and it is electroneutral (1H⁺: monocarboxylate-cotransport).

Figure 1. Principal of the pHAxensor assay. pHAxensor is a pH sensitive biosensor, a chimera between a pH-insensitive Red fluorescent protein (RFP) and a pH-sensitive Green fluorescent protein (GFP). pHAxensor shows high dynamic range for pH measurement in living cells and pKa around 7. The pH sensitivity in a full linear range is between 6.4-7.7. At acidic pH, GFP is quenched, whereas at physiological pH, GFP fluorescence increases.

Assay protocol

HEK-293 JumpIN-SLC16A3 cells were subjected to pharmacological characterization.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80-90% confluent flasks and seeded at 10'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in medium without the selective antibiotics and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂. 24h after seeding, cells were transiently transfected (Lipofectamine 2000 method) with the pH sensor construct (pHAxensor). At the same time cells were induced with 1 µg/mL Doxycycline (not induced and mock control in parallel).

pH biosensor assay

Medium was removed and cells were incubated in 20 µL/well of Tyrode Standard Buffer (pH 7.4 MES/HEPES) supplemented with 100 nM AZD3965 for 30 min at RT (AZD3965: MCT1 and MCT2 inhibitor, which displays no activity on MCT4).

Plates were analysed at FLIPR^{TETRA} reader using either the single read mode or the dual read mode:

Dual read mode							
Read Mode Name	Exc. Wlength(nm)	Em. Wlength(nm)	Gain	Exp. Time(s)	Exc. Intensity(%)	Gate Open(%)	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Read_Mode_1	510_545	565_625	2000	0.5300	70	19.62	→ pH insensitive domain
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Read_Mode_2	470_495	515_575	2000	0.5330	50	6.12	→ pH sensitive domain
Single read mode							
Read Mode Name	Exc. Wlength(nm)	Em. Wlength(nm)	Gain	Exp. Time(s)	Exc. Intensity(%)	Gate Open(%)	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Read_Mode_1	470_495	515_575	2000	0.5300	50	5.16	→ pH sensitive domain

To test pharmacology 20 µL/well of HCl (2X in Tyrode Buffer MES/HEPES) to reach a final pH of 6.8 or 7.0 (in addition to the basal condition of 7.4) in the presence or absence of a D/R of lactate (starting from 10 mM final concentration, semi-log dilution step, 8 concentrations, only buffer included) were online injected at the plate reader and fluorescence recorded.

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC16A3
Synonyms	Monocarboxylate Transporter 4, MCT4
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 16 (Monocarboxylic Acid Transporters)
UniProt ID	O15427
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE00TF-K (HEK-SLC16A3-WTOE-p5-6)

Assay data

<p>pH 6.8 (lactate 10 mM, lactate 3 mM, lactate 0 mM)</p> <p>pH 7.4 (lactate 10 mM, lactate 3 mM, lactate 0 mM)</p>	<p>Compound name (1)</p> <p>Lactate</p>
	<p>PubChem CID</p> <p>612</p>
	<p>Vendor (catalogue #)</p> <p>Sigma Aldrich, #L6402</p>
	<p>Mode of action</p> <p>Substrate</p>
	<p>Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)</p> <p>PoC = 30%</p> <p>The experiments were performed only upon transient transfection of the pH sensor. Only two doses of lactate were tested. From the recorded kinetics it is evident that the induced SLC16A3 cell line shows a specific response in acidic conditions, even if a lower response can be observed also in wt or uninduced cells, indicating an endogenous response to lactate. Both doses of lactate elicited a decrease of intracellular pH (a quenching of the fluorescence signal), which is about 30% more than the one observed in wt cells.</p>

Discussion

The pH biosensor assay for SLC16A3 showed that in the presence of protons, the two highest doses of lactate used (10 mM and 3 mM) induced a higher and specific quenching of the

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fluorescence signal in the target-induced condition. At the physiological pH, the transporter is almost completely inactive.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).